

ANALYSIS ON FOOD SECURITY, GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT (GDP) AND POPULATION OF SELECTED COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is to analyze the global food security index (GFSI), gross domestic product (GDP) and population in selected countries. The 113 countries were selected by the Economic Intelligence Unit (EIU) based on regional diversity, economic importance, population size and regions including the globe. Secondary data were used for analysis. The correlation between GFSI & GDP and GFSI & Population were studied. Top 10 countries and bottom 10 countries were ascertained based on GFSI. Box –plots for outliers were drawn for overall GFSI, Population and GDP. Winsorization technique was applied to minimize the influence of outliers in the data set. Correlation analysis was conducted to know the correlation between GFSI & GDP and GFSI & Population. The correlation between GDP and GFSI is weakly correlated. It is also seen that correlation between population and GFSI is not significant. Further correlation between GDP and Population is significant. GDP is moderately correlated with population. GFSI rank and median rank based on affordability, availability, quality & safety and natural resources & resilience were computed for each country to know the effect on overall food security score. This study was conducted and limited to the year 2019 only. .

Keywords: *Global food security index, gross domestic product, population, food security score indicators.*

Introduction

Food security is a situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutrition food that meets their dietary needs and food prepares for an active and healthy life (UN Food and Agriculture Organization). Food security not only carries significant benefits for human health, but also serves as the basis to achieve sustained economic growth. High rates of malnutrition can lead to a loss in gross domestic product (GDP) of as much as four to five percent. Multiple factors are responsible

for food insecurity worldwide, including population growth; climatic change, increasing cost of food, unemployment, poverty and loss of biodiversity.

Overall Global Food Security Index (GFSI) is a measurement tool that addresses the core issues of affordability, availability, quality & safety and natural resources & resilience in 113 countries around the world since its inception in 2011, the GFSI has become a policy benchmark for governments and a country diagnostic tool for investment and non-governmental organizations, multilaterals and academia have turned to the GFSI as a research tools to identify the countries in which to focus advocacy efforts for food-security policy changes and developments. This paper thus analyzes the dynamic relationship between GFSI & population and gross domestic product (GDP) of 113 countries.

The methodology for the GFSI was developed by the Economic Intelligent Unit with consultation from a peer panel of experts. The overall GFSI was computed considering four important parameters i.e affordability, availability, quality & safety and natural resources & resilience. Table 1 describes the important components of Global Food Security Index (GFSI).

Table 1: Important Components of Overall Global Food Security Index (GFSI)

Sl. No	Overall GFSI Components	Details
1	Affordability	Measures the ability of consumer to purchase food, their vulnerability to price shocks and the presence of programme and policies to support customers when shocks occur.
2	Availability	Measures the sufficiency of the national food supply, the risk of supply disruption, national capacity to disseminate food and research efforts to expand agricultural output.
3	Quality & Safety	Measures the variety and nutritional quality of average diets, as well as the safety of food.
4	Natural Resources & Resilience	Assesses a country's exposure to the impacts of climate change, its susceptibility to national resources risks and how the country is adapting to these risks.

Source: Economic Intelligence Unit (EIU)

Other Issues Connected with Food Security

The major other issues are: Population, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Agriculture production and Public distribution system. When population growth increases exponentially, the food short supply happens, because food supply will have a linear relationship on time line. Population increase will reduce the land availability for food production. There will be a mismatch between demand and supply, which can influence on price increase, reduction in consumption etc. Population increase will boost the GDP. Agriculture production will have an influence on GDP. Global Food Security Index (GFSI) and Global Hunger Index (GHI) are strongly associated.

Thousands went hungry even as food grains went waste

According to data provided by the Ministry of Consumer Affairs, around 1453 tons of food grains in the Food Corporation of India's warehouses were wasted in the month of June 2020 alone. It was in the months of April, May and June 2020 that millions of migrants to India's cities, who were thrown out of their jobs and left to struggle without food or shelter, were forced to trudge back to their villages. The government did release large volumes of grains and other food items for distribution among these migrant populations, but

still many went hungry. While this was mainly because of poor distribution processes, it is disturbing that even as millions of people were going hungry, tons of food grains were getting damaged in warehouses (Food wastes data, 2020).

The Global Hunger Index (GHI) is 'a tool designed to comprehensively measure and track hunger at the global, regional and national levels'. Data from the United Nations and other multilateral agencies are used for the calculation. India ranked 04th among 107 countries on the Global Hunger Index (GHI) that track undernourishment, child under nutrition and child mortality across the world. According to GHI report, 14 percent of India's population is undernourished (GHI Data, 2020).

Study objects and methods

Karolina Pawlak & Malgorzata (2020), the authors have focused not only on identifying the reasons of undernourishment, but also contributed to recognize the most effective ways to solve the hunger problem under a country's unique conditions. They have developed a comprehensive perspective for the policy formulation in various areas worldwide which may be of interest to scholars and policy makers.

According to Population Action Report (2020) almost one in seven people around the world are chronically hungry, lacking enough food to be healthy and lead active lives. According to FAO (2020) projections by 2050, population and economic growth will result in a doubling of demand for food globally.

Nur Marina Abdul Manap & Normaz Wana Ismail (2019), the researchers have identified that food security has a significant positive input on economic growth in terms of life expectancy, total employment and poverty.

Nighat Hanif, Madeela Nisa & Muhammed Rizwan Ya Seen (2019), these authors have found that GDP and population have a positive impact on food production index, while carbon dioxide(CO₂) and combustible renewable water (CRW) have also the negative relation with food production index.

Krystyna Swietlik (2018), the author has reported that higher levels of GDP were associated with high levels of food security and the biggest improvements in food security occurred in those countries with the fastest rise in GDP per capita.

E. Wesley & F. Peterson (2017), the author studied that the relationship between population growth and economic growth is controversial. Low population growth in high-income countries is likely to create social and economic problems while high population growth in low-income countries may slow their development.

Sudha Narayanan (2015) has highlighted the imperative of food security in India in the context of persistent prevalence of malnutrition despite several years of rapid growth. The crux of India's food problem today pertains not so much on increasing food availability or production but with the distribution of food.

Olivia F. Godbeer & Richard Wall (2014) have reported that Livestock production is an important contributor to sustainable food security for many nations, particularly in low income areas and marginal habitats that are unsuitable for crop production. Animal products account for approximately one-third of global human protein consumption.

Shri Dewi Applanaidu, Nor Aznin Abu Bakar & Amir Hussain Baharudin (2013), the authors have analyzed the dynamic relationship between selected macroeconomic variables (biodiesel production, exchange rate, government expenditure on rural development, Malaysia's GDP, food price index and Malaysia's population) and food security in Malaysia using A Vector Autoregressive Approach (VAR). It was found that all variables give shock / impact to food security.

Study Objectives

The main objectives of this research are:

- i. To analyze the overall Global Food Security Index (GFSI) of top 10 countries and bottom 10 countries out of 113 countries.
- ii. To detect the outliers with respect to overall score, population, and GDP.
- iii. To compute the absolute values of skewness and kurtosis before and after winsorization.
- iv. To ascertain the significance of various factors of GFSI, Population and GDP.
- v. To examine the GFSI Rank and Median Rank.

Methodology

Secondary data on GFSI, Population and GDP for the year 2019 were collected for 113 countries. The 113 countries in the index were selected by the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) based on regional diversity, economic importance, population size and the goal of including regions around the globe. Population and GDP of each country for the same year were collected from the secondary sources. MS Excel was used to tabulate the data. SPSS 24 was used for data analysis. The tabulated data in Excel Sheet is placed at **Annexure-1**.

Results and discussion

i. Top 10 Countries Overall Global Food Security Index

Table 2 shows the global food security index of top 10 countries. The country Finland ranks first position based on Overall GFSI 2019, followed by Ireland, Netherlands etc. Compared to 2018 index, the country Switzerland moved to 10th position from its top position.

Table 2: Top 10 Countries Overall Global Food Security Index

Sl. No	Country	Overall Score
1	Finland	85.3
2	Ireland	83.8
3	Netherlands	79.9
4	Austria	79.4
5	Czech Republic	78.6
6	United Kingdom	78.5
7	Sweden	78.1
8	Israel	78.0
9	Japan	77.9
10	Switzerland	77.7

Figure 1: Top 10 Countries Overall Score

ii. Bottom 10 Countries Overall Global Food Security Index

Table 3 shows the overall global food security index of bottom 10 countries. The countries like Yemen, and Sudan ranks lowest positions based on Overall GFSI 2019. Zambia, Sudan and Yemen rank at the bottom of the table.

Table 3: Bottom 10 Countries Overall Global Food Security Index

Sl. No	Country	Overall Score
104	Rwanda	38.8
105	Haiti	38.5
106	Madagascar	37.5
107	Burundi	37.1
108	Siera Leone	37.0
109	Ethiopia	37.0
110	Malawi	36.7
111	Zambia	36.6
112	Sudan	36.0
113	Yemen	35.7

Figure 2: Bottom 10 Countries Overall Score

iii. Box-Plot for outlier detection

Box plots are drawn to show the outliers within a data set. Outlier is defined as a data point that is located outside the whisker of the box plot. Figure 3 shows the box-plot of overall global food security index. It gives an idea that the data set falls in the Inter-Quartile Range (IQR).

Overall GFSI

Figure 3: Overall GFSI

iv. Detection of outlier in Population

Table 4 outlines the top 10 countries (outliers) population based on 2019 data. China and India are ranks top in population. Japan's overall GFSI is 9th position and in population it occupies 10th position.

Table 4: Outlier in Population

Sl. No	Country	Population (Crores)
1	China	139.77
2	India	136.64
3	USA	32.82
4	Indonesia	27.06
5	Pakistan	21.66
6	Brazil	21.30
7	Nigeria	20.10
8	Bangladesh	16.30
9	Mexico	12.76
10	Japan	12.63

Figure 4: Box- Plot for outlier detection - Population

Figure 4 shows the outliers in population. The countries like China and India are outliers in population. Further, the countries like USA, Indonesia, Pakistan, Brazil and Nigeria are also outliers in population.

v. Detection of outliers in Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Table 5 shows the outliers in GDP based on 2019 data. United States and China ranks 1st and 2nd position respectively. India stands at 5th position. Other countries like India, France, South Korea and Taiwan are growing economy countries.

Table 5: Outlier in Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Sl. No	Country	GDP (Cr. In USD)
1	USA	21,43,00,000
2	China	14,34,00,000
3	Japan	5,08,00,000
4	Germany	3,86,00,000
5	India	2,87,00,000
6	United Kingdom	2,83,00,000
7	France	2,72,00,000
8	Italy	2,00,00,000
9	Brazil	1,84,00,000
10	Canada	1,74,00,000

Figure 5: Box-Plot for outlier detection - GDP

vi. Top 10 Countries overall GFSI, Population and GDP

Table 6 shows the top 10 countries overall GFSI, Population and GDP. Around 60 percentage of the country’s population is less than one crore. Japan’s population is more than 12 Crs and GDP 5.08 trillion dollars, whereas United Kingdom’s population is more than 6 Crs and GDP 2.83 trillion dollars.

Table 6: Top 10 Countries GFSI, Population and GDP

Sl. No	Country	Overall GFSI Score	Population (In Crores)	GDP (In Crores USD)
1	Finland	85.3	0.552	26,929.63
2	Ireland	83.8	0.490	38,869.87
3	Netherlands	79.9	1.730	90,705.09
4	Austria	79.4	0.886	44,507.54
5	Czech Republic	78.6	1.06	25,068.05
6	United Kingdom	78.5	6.66	2,83,00,000.00
7	Sweden	78.1	1.02	53,088.39
8	Israel	78.0	0.905	39,465.22
9	Japan	77.9	12.63	5,08,00,000.00
10	Switzerland	77.7	0.853	70,308.24

vii. Outliers detection – Absolute value of skewness and kurtosis before and after winsorization

Winsorization is a way to minimize the influence of outliers in the data set either by assigning the outlier a lower weight or changing the value so that it is close to other values in the set (Kotz, et al, 2006, Rand Wilcox, 2017).

Table 7 shows the outlier detection – Indicators with an absolute value of skewness greater than 2 and an absolute value of kurtosis greater than 3.5. Variables like overall GFSI, Population, GDP, Affordability, Availability, Quality & Safety and Natural Resources & Resilience are the outliers’ indicators. For all these variables, before winsorization and after winsorization are computed. Population and GDP are having the more than the stipulated values of skewness and kurtosis before winsorization. Only population has kurtosis value more than 3 after winsorization. All other variables are having lower values in respect of skewness and kurtosis. Skewness value for standard normal distribution is zero. Kurtosis value for standard normal distribution is 3.

Table 7: Outlier detection- Indicators with an absolute value of skewness greater than 2 and an absolute value of kurtosis greater than 3.5

Variables	Before Winsorization		After Winsorization	
	Skewness	Kurtosis	Skewness	Kurtosis
Overall Score	0.27	1.10	1.10	0.00
Population	6.49	44.29	1.908	3.406
GDP	6.69	49.32	1.014	0.168
Affordability	0.54	1.03	1.03	0.00
Availability	0.40	0.41	0.41	0.00
Quality & Safety	0.15	1.29	1.29	0.00
Natural Resources & Resilience	0.75	0.52	0.52	0.00

viii. Difference of Country Ranking before and after the winsorization

Table 8 shows the difference of country ranking before and after the winsorization. China’s rank difference is zero and stands on top. Japan, Canada, Russia, and Brazil follow China.

Table 8: Difference of Country ranking before and after the winsorization

Rank Difference	Percentage	Countries
0	93.81	China(-1)
+/-1	1.77	Japan(-2)
+/-2	1.77	
+/-3	1.77	
4	0.88	
Shift by more than 3 positions		Canada(4), Russia (3), Brazil (-3)

ix. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical method used to evaluate the strength of relationships between two quantitative variables. A high correlation means that two or more variables have a strong relationship with each other, while a weak correlation means that the variables are hardly related. Table 9 shows the correlation analysis among variables. The correlation between GDP and GFSI is 0.227 which is weakly correlated significant at the level of 0.05. It is also seen that correlation between population and GFSI is 0.08 and not significant at 0.05 levels. Further correlation between GDP and Population is 0.56 and significant at 0.01 levels. GDP is moderately correlated with population.

Table 9: Correlation Analysis

S.N.	Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Overall Score	0.499	0.276	1						
2	Population	0.045	0.133	0.018	1					
3	GDP	0.028	0.118	.227*	.561**	1				
4	Affordability	0.644	0.282	.960**	-0.020	.187*	1			
5	Availability	0.547	0.213	.866**	0.161	.265**	.752**	1		
6	Quality and Safety	0.562	0.298	.931**	-0.023	.223*	.869**	.739**	1	
7	Natural Resources & Resilience	0.409	0.218	.589**	-0.098	0.078	.476**	.397**	.547**	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

x. Weight scheme versus Importance of each dimension

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) is used to identify the patterns in the data set. It is also to find the relationships in data. Table 10 shows the weight scheme versus Statistical importance of each dimension. The overall GFSI has a very strong relationship with affordability, quality & safety and availability. But it has a weak relationship with GDP.

Table 10: Weight Scheme versus Statistical Importance of each dimension

Indicators	Overall GFSI score	
	Weight	Squared Pearson Correlation
Affordability	40%	92.20%
Availability	44%	75.00%
Quality & Safety	16%	86.70%
GDP	22.22%	05.15%

xi. Country Overall GFSI Rank and Median Ranks of its Components

Rank is calculated based on Overall GFSI and Median rank is computed based on Affordability, Availability, Quality & Safety and Natural Resources & Resilience. Table 11 shows the country overall food security score rank and median rank based on affordability, availability, quality & safety and natural resources & resilience for each country. Finland rank based on overall food security score is 1 and median rank is 3. Similarly, India's overall score rank is 71 and median rank is 75.

Table 11: Country Overall GFSI Rank and Median Rank

Country Name	Rank	Median rank	Country Name	Rank	Median rank	Country Name	Rank	Median rank
Finland	1	3	China	39	45	Nepal	77	79.5
Ireland	2	2.5	Slovakia	40	32	Ghana	77	82.5
Netherlands	3	9	Panama	41	39	Mali	79	64
Austria	4	10	UAE	42	41	Pakistan	80	81
Czech Republic	5	19.5	Malaysia	43	51	Cambodia	81	85.5
United Kingdom	6	10.5	Bulgaria	44	44	Cote d'Ivoire	82	77
Sweden	7	9.5	Mexico	45	48.5	Uzbekistan	83	73
Israel	8	7	Peru	46	52	Bangladesh	84	94
Japan	9	11.5	Turkey	47	48	Tajikistan	85	81
Switzerland	10	15.5	Dominican Republic	48	50	Kenya	86	76.5
USA	11	13.5	Bahrain	49	54	Niger	87	87
Canada	12	18.5	Brazil	50	58	Burkina Faso	88	81
New Zealand	13	20	Thailand	51	55	Tanzania	89	87.5
Germany	13	15	Serbia	52	56	Senegal	90	89
Italy	15	16.5	Colombia	53	52.5	Laos	90	87.5
Denmark	15	15.5	Ukraine	54	50	Benin	92	91
France	17	13.5	Argentina	55	63	Togo	93	82.5
Norway	18	22	Azerbaijan	56	61	Cameroon	94	89
Singapore	19	27.5	Morocco	57	53.5	Uganda	95	96.5
Portugal	19	20	Algeria	58	66	Venezuela	96	98.5
Belgium	21	18.5	Tunisia	59	60.5	Angola	97	93
Romania	22	22.5	Egypt	60	54.5	Congo Demo Repub	98	97
Belarus	23	27	Paraguay	61	64	Mozambique	99	96.5
Russia	24	28.5	Jordan	62	55	Nigeria	100	101.5
Poland	25	27.5	Vietnam	63	65.5	Syria	101	99
Spain	26	22.5	Bolivia	64	62	Guinea	102	102.5

Country Name	Rank	Median rank	Country Name	Rank	Median rank	Country Name	Rank	Median rank
Greece	27	30	Indonesia	65	72	Chad	103	96.5
Costa Rica	28	35	El Salvador	66	66	Rwanda	104	89
South Korea	29	29.5	Honduras	67	53	Haiti	105	98.5
Uruguay	30	38.5	Ecuador	68	71.5	Madagascar	106	105.5
Australia	31	37	South Africa	69	61	Burundi	107	103
Kazakhstan	32	33	Myanmar	70	70.5	Siera Leone	108	105
Kuwait	33	29.5	India	71	75	Ethiopia	108	101.5
Oman	34	43	Guatemala	71	75	Malawi	110	101
Chile	34	33	Philippines	73	74.5	Zambia	111	107.5
Hungary	36	37	Botswana	74	82	Sudan	112	96.5
Qatar	37	34.5	Sri Lanka	75	71.5	Yemen	113	102.5
Saudi Arabia	38	41	Nicaragua	76	74.5			

Figure 6: Overall Global Food Security Index Rank and Median Rank

Figure 6 shows the overall GFSI rank and median ranks on four elements for all the 113 countries. Overall score rank follows in a linear pattern (in blue line), whereas median rank spikes above below the overall rank line. Median ranks are calculated based on four elements (availability, affordability, quality & safety and natural resources & resilience). Ranks are more sensitive than median ranks (Brian Martin, 2016).

Top ten countries Global Food Security Index (GFSI) rankings during last three years

Table 12 shows top ten countries Global Food Security Index (GFSI) rankings during the last three years. i.e 2019, 2020 and 2021.

Table 12: Top ten countries Global Food Security Index (GFSI) rankings during 2019, 2020 and 2021

Countries	2019	2020	2021
Finland	1	4	4
Ireland	2	1	1
Netherland	3	6	6
Austria	4	2	2
Czek Republic	5	---	---
United Kingdom	6	3	3
Sweden	7	---	---
Israel	8	8	---
Japan	9	9	8
Switzerland	10	10	5
Canada	---	---	7
France	---	---	9
USA	---	---	10

Source: The Economic Intelligence Unit (EIU) Reports 2019, 2020 and 2021)

In table 12, it is found that the countries like Czek Republic, Sweden and Israel were not there in GFSI rankings 2021. The countries like Canada, France and USA were occupied top ten GFSI rankings in the 2021. It is also seen that the countries like Ireland, Finland, Netherland, Austria, United Kingdom, Japan, and Switzerland are able to perform better consistently. It is found that the public distribution policy, agricultural productivity, support & assistance to farmers, export policy, creation of agricultural infrastructure and tackling supply chain issues played a key role in their food security programs.

Conclusion

In this paper, the authors have analyzed the overall global food security index in selected 113 countries based on the Economic Intelligence Unit (EIU) report 2019. The top 10 countries overall score and bottom 10 countries overall were analyzed. The countries like Finland, Ireland, Netherlands etc stands at top position. India occupies 71st positions. The countries like Rwanda, Haiti, Madagascar etc occupies at the lowest positions based on global food security score. The outliers in population were computed. The countries like China, India etc stands on top in population. Similarly, the outliers in GDP are also computed. The countries like USA, China, Japan etc stands on top. India takes 5th position in this. The correlation between GDP and GFSI is 0.227 which is weakly correlated significant at the level of 0.05. It is also seen that correlation between population and GFSI is 0.08 and not significant at 0.05 levels. Further correlation between GDP and Population is 0.56 and significant at 0.01 levels. GDP is moderately correlated with population.

In the overall food security score, affordability, availability and quality & safety takes higher weight age than that of GDP (Squared Pearson Correlation is 5.15% only). It is difficult for India to achieve USD 5 trillion economies in the year 2026 (as predicted) to reach top 10 positions based on GFSI. This is great challenge ahead of India. India should more focus on affordability, availability and quality & safety to boost its overall GFSI.

The thrust areas are: gross domestic product per capita, food safety-net programs, access to financing for farmers, sufficiency of food supply, agricultural infrastructure, crop storage facilities – cold chain, food wastages, public distribution system, food safety, dietary diversity, climatic change, resources management-land, water, oceans, population growth and urbanization. India should focus on improving the above indicators to improve its overall food security score.

Scope for further Research

There is larger scope available to conduct further research. Other macroeconomic indicators like agricultural production, products price, gross domestic product per capita, purchasing power, consumption level, natural resources management, public distribution systems and public policies may be considered specifically for further research.

Conflicts of interests

The authors have declared that there is no conflict of interests.

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Annexure -1

Global Ranking	Country	GFSI	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Finland	85.3	90.6	82.0	93.8	73.2	0.552	26,929.63
2	Ireland	83.8	92.2	75.7	94.0	73.2	0.49	38,869.87
3	Netherlands	79.9	90.7	74.5	88.7	61.5	1.73	90,705.09
4	Austria	79.4	89.5	70.8	94.3	61.8	0.886	44,507.54
5	Czech Repub	78.6	86.3	70.4	87.1	70.9	1.06	25,068.05
6	UK	78.5	89.7	70.0	92.8	59.4	6.66	2,83,00,000.00
7	Sweden	78.1	89.2	65.0	92.3	67.4	1.02	53,088.39
8	Israel	78.0	89.5	75.3	93.9	46.3	0.905	39,465.22
9	Japan	77.9	90.4	73.0	83.4	58.6	12.63	5,08,00,000.00
10	Switzerland	77.7	87.9	68.4	89.6	64.2	8.853	70,308.24
11	USA	77.5	87.8	72.2	94.3	51.4	32.82	21,43,00,000.00
12	Canada	77.2	85.3	72.0	94.5	54.5	3.76	1,74,00,000.00
13	New Zealand	77.0	90.6	64.0	83.1	69.9	0.492	20,692.88
13	Germany	77.0	87.7	71.6	91.3	52.9	8.30	3,86,00,000.00
15	Italy	76.6	89.8	71.4	88.0	50.7	6.04	2,00,00,000.00
15	Denmark	76.6	92.2	64.1	89.7	57.6	0.581	35,010.43
17	France	76.5	88.3	65.8	92.0	59.0	6.71	2,72,00,000.00
18	Norway	76.2	81.1	65.0	90.6	73.5	0.532	40,333.64
19	Singapore	75.7	87.3	75.8	82.3	47.4	0.57	37,206.25
19	Portugal	75.7	87.0	68.5	92.3	51.8	1.03	23,878.51
21	Belgium	75.2	88.2	69.6	88.4	48.2	1.15	53,309.75
22	Romania	74.2	82.8	67.9	87.2	56.7	1.94	25,007.74
23	Belarus	73.8	85.0	65.8	85.5	56.3	0.947	6,308.05
24	Russia	73.7	87.2	64.7	84.1	55.0	14.44	1,70,00,000.00
25	Poland	73.5	85.1	65.8	83.6	56.5	3.80	59,585.82
26	Spain	73.4	86.3	61.0	87.5	58.4	4.69	1,39,00,000.00
27	Greece	73.0	86.9	63.6	85.5	52.5	1.07	20,985.28
28	Costa Rica	72.3	83.9	60.8	78.4	66.0	0.505	6,180.14
29	South Korea	72.1	81.8	67.7	78.4	56.1	5.17	1,65,00,000.00
30	Uruguay	71.4	76.6	60.7	84.4	68.6	0.346	5,604.59
31	Australia	71.3	83.7	62.4	87.8	48.3	2.54	1,40,00,000.00
32	Kazakhstan	70.8	79.0	65.7	83.7	52.4	1.85	18,166.59
33	Kuwait	70.7	82.5	68.3	86.4	37.2	0.421	13,462.85
34	Oman	70.2	88.5	59.1	83.7	43.8	0.497	7,633.15
34	Chile	70.2	77.0	66.1	80.5	54.7	1.90	28,231.82
36	Hungary	70.1	81.7	60.6	80.9	55.6	0.977	16,346.90

37	Qatar	69.6	80.3	70.7	84.3	33.6	0.283	17,583.76
38	Saudi Arabia	69.5	79.6	73.0	79.8	34.1	3.43	79,296.68
39	China	69.3	72.8	73.7	72.5	51.2	139.77	14,34,00,000.00
40	Slovakia	69.2	88.1	51.7	72.9	62.9	0.545	10,507.97
41	Panama	68.9	78.0	66.6	72.5	53.0	0.425	6,680.08
Global Ranking	Country	GFSI	1	2	3	4	5	6
42	UAE	68.3	73.0	66.5	88.8	42.4	0.977	42,114.23
43	Malaysia	67.9	85.5	58.8	72.5	47.5	3.19	36,468.14
44	Bulgaria	67.4	80.0	57.3	74.1	56.0	0.70	6,855.88
45	Mexico	66.2	76.0	61.8	76.6	45.7	12.76	1,27,00,000.00
46	Peru	65.7	78.2	63.1	66.8	46.6	3.25	22,684.81
47	Turkey	65.3	66.0	67.2	78.3	47.4	8.2	76,142.55
48	Dominician Reb	65.2	75.9	62.1	67.4	49.0	1.08	8,894.13
49	Bahrain	64.6	82.6	56.8	76.7	33.7	0.164	3,857.41
50	Brazil	64.1	71.5	52.4	88.9	47.1	21.1	1,84,00,000.00
51	Thailand	64.0	82.8	55.3	59.5	50.0	6.96	54,354.90
52	Serbia	63.2	83.2	43.9	80.3	45.0	0.694	5,147.50
53	Colombia	63.1	65.8	58.5	74.1	55.4	5.03	32,361.60
54	Ukraine	63.0	74.4	51.6	75.3	50.3	4.44	15,378.11
55	Argentina	62.7	60.5	59.6	90.2	44.9	4.49	44,544.52
56	Azerbaijan	62.3	75.9	63.3	60.9	37.1	1.0	4,804.76
57	Morocco	62.0	76.3	51.4	67.4	49.5	3.65	11,970.03
58	Algeria	61.8	78.7	55.7	62.0	42.0	4.31	17,109.13
59	Tunisia	61.4	69.0	56.7	70.8	46.7	1.17	3,879.67
60	Egypt	61.1	51.8	75.2	64.3	49.4	10.04	30,309.23
61	Paraguay	60.5	80.7	44.2	68.6	45.0	0.704	3,814.53
62	Jordan	60.4	77.1	48.2	63.1	49.5	1.01	4,450.29
63	Vietnam	60.3	66.7	61.3	61.4	45.9	9.65	26,192.12
64	Bolivia	60.0	72.0	52.2	65.5	46.5	1.15	4,089.53
65	Indonesia	59.5	73.5	64.7	49.6	34.1	27.06	1,12,00,000.00
66	El Salvador	59.0	63.8	60.9	62.1	43.9	0.645	2,702.26
67	Honduras	58.2	52.2	64.0	61.6	55.4	0.975	2,509.54
68	Ecuador	57.9	68.3	50.7	65.7	43.9	1.74	10,743.57
69	South Africa	57.8	63.1	49.5	72.4	49.0	5.86	35,143.16
70	Myanmar	56.6	58.1	53.9	59.3	56.3	5.40	7,608.59
71	India	56.2	55.0	64.3	59.0	40.8	136.64	2,87,00,000.00
71	Guatemala	56.2	57.6	61.8	56.5	43.2	1.66	7,671.04
73	Philippines	55.7	66.5	57.6	52.0	35.8	10.81	37,679.55
74	Botswana	55.5	70.3	47.6	59.3	39.2	0.23	1,834.05
75	Sri Lanka	54.8	64.0	51.8	52.0	46.3	2.18	8,400.88
76	Nicaragua	54.4	61.9	49.0	55.4	49.5	0.655	1,252.09
77	Nepal	53.0	54.6	58.8	48.0	44.2	2.86	3,064.14
77	Ghana	53.0	61.4	49.6	54.6	42.3	3.04	6,698.36
79	Mali	52.7	45.8	58.1	61.2	47.1	1.97	1,727.96
80	Pakistan	52.3	51.1	57.7	54.8	42.1	21.66	27,822.19
81	Cambodia	51.5	57.5	57.4	40.1	41.2	1.65	2,708.94
82	CotedIvoire	51.0	50.3	53.0	46.3	53.5	2.57	5,853.94
83	Uzbekistan	50.9	47.1	50.6	62.1	47.4	3.36	5,792.13
84	Bangladesh	50.0	48.3	64.4	40.9	35.8	16.3	30,257.13
Global Ranking	Country	GFSI	1	2	3	4	5	6
85	Tajikistan	49.4	52.7	50.9	53.1	37.0	0.932	811.66

86	Kenya	49.0	53.2	41.8	58.6	45.0	5.26	9,550.31
87	Niger	47.6	41.8	48.8	51.7	52.0	2.33	1,291.17
88	Burkina Fasco	47.4	45.4	52.5	45.9	43.5	2.03	1,599.08
89	Tanzania	47.1	41.4	52.8	51.2	42.8	5.8	6,317.71
90	Senegal	46.4	44.7	45.0	55.8	42.5	1.63	2,357.81
90	Laos	46.4	45.8	47.8	46.2	45.1	0.717	1,817.38
92	Benin	46.2	44.2	54.8	48.3	32.2	1.18	1,439.07
93	Togo	44.9	41.4	53.4	35.1	45.4	0.808	549.03
94	Cameroon	44.7	45.5	41.0	48.4	46.2	2.59	3,900.74
95	Uganda	42.9	38.2	44.4	46.0	45.5	4.43	3,516.52
96	Venezuela	42.8	37.9	35.2	68.3	40.6	2.85	48,235.93
97	Angola	42.1	32.7	45.3	48.6	47.1	3.18	8,881.57
98	Congo De. Rep	40.7	32.4	47.4	39.6	44.5	8.68	5,040.07
99	Mozambiques	40.6	33.0	49.9	36.0	42.0	3.04	1,529.14
100	Nigeria	40.1	32.9	46.8	41.5	39.3	20.1	44,812.04
101	Syria	40.0	29.3	41.3	55.6	41.5	1.71	4,040.50
102	Guinea	39.5	31.3	47.4	39.4	40.6	1.28	1,229.67
103	Chad	39.4	43.6	32.2	42.5	41.7	1.59	1,131.50
104	Rwanda	38.8	21.5	45.6	52.1	44.8	1.26	1,035.44
105	Haiti	38.5	37.4	32.8	45.3	44.4	1.13	1,433.22
106	Madagascar	37.5	31.4	38.6	39.9	44.5	2.70	1,411.46
107	Burundi	37.1	30.6	35.0	42.5	47.3	1.15	301.23
108	Sirerra Leone	37.0	35.3	32.7	33.1	52.3	0.781	412.17
108	Ethiopia	37.0	27.7	42.1	42.4	39.2	11.21	9,591.26
110	Malawi	36.7	18.3	42.9	41.7	54.0	1.86	766.67
111	Zambia	36.6	27.4	40.4	36.4	46.6	1.76	2,330.98
112	Sudan	36.0	27.6	30.8	52.7	44.5	4.28	3,051.35
113	Yemen	35.7	40.3	27.5	36.9	41.2	2.92	2,285.11

Note:

1. Column Numbered ' 1 ' indicates ' Affordability ' Score out of 100
2. Column Numbered ' 2 ' indicates ' Availability ' Score out of 100
3. Column Numbered ' 3 ' indicates ' Quality & Safety ' Score out of 100
4. Column Numbered ' 4 ' indicates ' National Resources & Resilience ' Score out 100
5. Column Numbered ' 5 ' indicates ' Population ' in Crores
6. Column Numbered ' 6 ' indicates ' Gross Domestic Product ' in USD Crores